

JOURNALISM AND NEWSPAPER WRITING

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Summary

Although journalism was initially rooted in newspaper publishing, today newspapers are gradually disappearing. This trend is observed worldwide. The decline in readership and the reduction in the number of newspapers have several causes. It cannot be explained by a single factor. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the rapid development of information and communication technologies is one of the factors leading to significant transformations in journalism. One of the main manifestations of these transformations is the gradual fading of newspaper publishing. However, the press can still maintain its existence. This shows that there is still a need for the press. No matter how advanced technology becomes, it cannot fulfill many of the functions of classical journalism.

Keywords: journalism, press, media, information and communication technologies, newspaper

Introduction

The foundation of journalism was laid with the printed press. This is true for all countries. Such similarity is not accidental; it is directly related to

the development prospects of scientific and technical progress in a given period. Journalism in Azerbaijan began in 1875 with the newspaper “Əkinçi”, in Turkey in 1831 with “Taqvimi Vakayi”, and in Russia in 1756 with “Moskovskie Vedemosti”. In Europe, however, the history of journalism dates back to the 17th–18th centuries.

According to many theorists, true journalism lies in newspapers. “Newspapers are not only a means of information but also a culture of thought. Even when readership decreases, these publications remain the main pillars of our national information history” [1].

The principles of transparency and democracy, which play the most important role in the fair governance of society, can only be realized through mass media [2]. At different times, this process has always remained relevant. The point is that successful governance of society requires the ability to influence public opinion, which is impossible without media. In this regard, throughout history—even when journalism had not yet developed as a profession—media elements were used to shape public consciousness. Various cave paintings and hieroglyphs can serve as examples of this.

Nevertheless, media has constantly transformed. As noted, this transformation is directly linked to the development of scientific and technical progress, as well as the new functions of media and the expectations placed upon it.

The Past, Present, and Future of Print Media

The sequence of changes in the form of media is the same for all countries. First came newspapers, then radio, and later television. “Journalism has experienced several revolutionary leaps in its history. The emergence of newspaper production, the invention of circulation techniques, the appearance of radio—which once seemed miraculous—and later television are proof of this” [2].

With the development of artificial intelligence, an entirely new stage has begun in the field of media. Robot technologies not only write instead of journalists but also think and make decisions in their place. “Artificial intelligence is increasingly penetrating the work of media” [3].

Undoubtedly, advancing technology offers new opportunities for media. This not only changes the format of journalism and the working principles of journalists but also introduces new tendencies for the audience. Today, preparing material is as easy for journalists as accessing news is convenient for readers. Although the rapid spread of technology into the press creates serious advantages, it also brings shortcomings and deficiencies. Professional journalism is gradually fading, or the criteria of professionalism are changing.

Not only the audience but even journalists themselves have begun to lose trust in media. There are several reasons for this. First, the ease with which material can be deleted or edited

on new media platforms. Second, the growing haste and carelessness, where the principle of speed outweighs objectivity, leading to an increase in inaccurate news. Third, journalism itself has become an alternative field for many.

Interestingly, despite the rapid development of technology and revolutionary changes in the mass media system, newspapers still continue to operate. Two main tendencies can be observed here. First, in some countries newspapers are gradually disappearing. The reasons include technological development, the rise of alternative information sources, the demands of the “age of speed” (for example, if an event occurs today but is published in a newspaper tomorrow, it is often considered irrelevant), economic difficulties, and other factors. In many countries, governments no longer wish to allocate funds or attention to the press. This is especially observed in former CIS countries, including Azerbaijan. As a result of government policies toward the press, some newspapers are closed, or their frequency and number of pages are reduced. This ultimately affects both the quantity and quality of press outlets. “As is known, the 21st century is the age of new technologies, the internet, and speed. But the 21st century will also go down in history as the decline era of newspapers, that is, print media. The problem has been advancing rapidly since the first days of the new century and is already at our doorstep. Print media is quickly losing its position” [4].

It is noteworthy that technology is also advancing in Western countries. In fact, most Western nations are ahead of the East in the field of information and communication technologies, meaning media has more diverse and modern opportunities. Nevertheless, newspapers in both the USA and Europe still maintain their prestige. True, the press no longer has as large an audience as before, but in various Western countries newspapers such as “The Times”, “The Washington Post”, and “Le Figaro” are still published.

The situation of the press in Turkey is also quite good. Newspapers are rich both in quantity and quality. Publications are colorful, multi-paged, and printed on quality paper. Moreover, press outlets publish sufficiently interesting and readable materials. Thus, newspapers attract attention both in content and design.

This raises the question: What will be the future of the press? It is clear that advancing technology will increasingly affect newspaper publishing. Nevertheless, considering the advantages of newspapers and their role as the core of journalism, we must think about ways to keep the press alive. First, problems must be identified and resolved. As noted, one of the main issues undermining newspaper publishing is economic instability. If governments are no longer interested in financing newspapers, the press must solve its own financial problems. In other words, the press must become self-financing. Newspaper editorial offices should not only cover their expenses

but also generate profit. Two key factors are needed for this. First, the subscription system must be developed. It is known that retail newspaper sales are not very widespread, and the income from such sales is not significant. Therefore, various organizations and institutions should subscribe to different publications. Second, the advertising market must be developed. Allocating space in newspapers for advertisements of different products and services means considerable income. “In Azerbaijan, there are no mailboxes or postmen left. If a newspaper is delivered to the reader in the afternoon, they will no longer use it, because by then they will have already received the news from social networks and websites. Thus, the subscription system for newspapers in our country has collapsed. Unless accessibility to newspapers is restored and the quality of their content improved, newspaper publishing will perish” [5].

It should also be noted that neither the advertising market nor the subscription system in Azerbaijan collapsed overnight. Newspaper editorial offices themselves are largely to blame. Unlike many European countries, the Azerbaijani press failed to adapt to the demands of the new era. Yet, the French government considers print media “the pillar of democracy” and allocates substantial financial support to newspapers every year. These funds are not direct subsidies but are provided in the form of tax breaks, reduced postal delivery costs,

and subsidies for paper production. For example, newspapers such as “Le Monde” and “Le Figaro” benefit from this model, continuing both print and online development.

In Japan, the center of technology, newspaper reading is still part of daily life. The circulation of “Yomiuri Shimbun” is close to 8 million—the highest in the world. The secret lies in maintaining the system of delivering newspapers to homes every morning and sustaining strong trust with readers [5].

So how should the advertising market and subscription system be developed? First, the prestige of newspapers, their credibility, and trust must be restored. Newspapers should be viewed as alternative sources of news. The press should not remain in the shadow of new media.

A situation must be created where the press preserves its originality. Different solutions are proposed for this. For example, some experts argue that since websites and news agencies surpass the press in terms of breaking news, newspapers should focus more on in-depth investigative articles. This idea has some truth. Indeed, publishing dynamic events in newspapers sometimes reduces interest, as people are already informed about the incident. Moreover, events change, and the news loses relevance. Therefore, newspapers should prioritize interviews, articles, and reports rather than breaking news. In this regard, Azerbaijan’s “525th Newspaper”, which continues

publishing and has a permanent readership, is characteristic. Perhaps the success of “525” lies in its approach of working on topics more analytically or in a publicistic context. “The 525th Newspaper did not chase after sensationalism, never deceived readers with exaggerated news, shocking headlines, rumors, fabrications, or gossip. That is why it won the appreciation of discerning readers who seek truth, not sensation, and expect thought-provoking ideas” [6].

On the other hand, many editors-in-chief and experienced journalists suggest that newspapers and their websites should work in coordination. This practice exists worldwide. What does it mean? It means that a preview or the first few paragraphs of an article are published online, and readers are encouraged to read the rest in the newspaper. This strategy can increase interest in newspapers.

Another frequently discussed suggestion is the regular publication of crosswords and horoscope forecasts in newspapers. Global experience shows that these features attract readers. Sometimes people buy newspapers not for the news but precisely for such additional elements.

Conclusion

In general, international experience also shows that for newspapers to preserve their existence, they must transform into business entities. Today, media outlets that are still published and read in different countries have managed to achieve

this. In Azerbaijan, however, this has not been observed.

As a result, it can be said that newspapers have lost their former position due to objective reasons. Nevertheless, despite all these factors, the press still continues its activity. This is the clearest example of the ongoing need for traditional journalism. “Despite the development of the internet, newspapers remain vital for several reasons: reliability and trust, in-depth reporting, accountability and watchdog role, community connection, support for democracy, and educational resource” [7].

It is evident that newspaper publishing holds a unique place in the media environment. This means that even if the format of the press changes in the future, traditional journalism will still be able to preserve its existence for many years to come.

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